

Analytical Applications of 5-Amino-2,4-Pyrimidinediol and its Azo-Dyes

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5-Amino-2,4-pyrimidinediol has been used for spectrophotometric determination of Ru(III) and micro-detection of Os(VIII). Manyfold concentrations of diverse ions including those from platinum group metals do not interfere. The diol coupled with diazotised sulphanilic acid finds use as a chelometric indicator in the determination of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II). 1-(2,4-Dihydroxy-5-pyrimidylazo)-2-naphthol is used as an indicator in determination of MoO_4^{2-} , WO_4^{2-} and PO_4^{3-} via titrations with lead nitrate solution.

SEVERAL pyrimidines have been recently developed in our laboratory as analytical reagents¹⁻⁶ for micro-detection and determination of iron and platinum group metals. This paper describes the use of 5-amino-2,4-pyrimidinediol (I) for spectrophotometric determination of Ru(III) and micro-detection of Os(VIII). Its azo dyes (II) and (III) are used as indicators in titrations of the metal ions Zn, Cd and Hg and anions MoO_4^{2-} , WO_4^{2-} and PO_4^{3-} , respectively.

Experimental

Stock solutions of Ru(III) and Os(VIII) were prepared from reagent grade $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and OsO_4 by dissolving them in 1N HCl and 5N NaOH, respectively. 5-Amino-2,4-pyrimidinediol being sparingly soluble in water was dissolved in 0.1N NaOH to prepare its standard solution. All other solutions were prepared from analytical reagent grade chemicals and deionized water.

Absorbance readings were taken by a Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer. A Metrohm pH meter, E-350, was used for measuring pH of the solutions.

Results and Discussion

5-Amino-2,4-pyrimidinediol forms a red complex with Ru(III) at pH 2.9-4.0 with a molar extinction coefficient of 7600 at 480 nm. About 170 times molar excess of the reagent over metal is needed for full development of the colour. The system obeys Beer's law up to 6.7 ppm of the metal concentration with a standard deviation of 0.0055. The diol also forms a violet complex at pH 5.4-6.1 with molar extinction coefficient of 9600 at 580 nm. Nearly 170 times molar excess of the diol is required for full complexation. The system obeys Beer's law up to 4.8 ppm of ruthenium concentration with a standard deviation of 0.0060.

Determination of Ru(III) : To a suitable aliquot of the metal solution, add sufficient excess of the diol and adjust pH between 2.9-4.0. Heat the solution on a steam bath for 1 hr, cool it and make up the volume. Note the absorbance at 480 nm against the reagent blank prepared under the same conditions.

Interferences : Making use of the red complex at pH 3.0 in determination of 3.3 ppm of ruthenium, the tolerance limits of other ions are : F^- (300) ; Cl^- (5000) ; Br^- (3000) ; I^- (500) ; NO_3^- (1000) ; SCN^- (50) ; SO_4^{2-} (1000) ; PO_4^{3-} (10) ; Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} or Ba^{2+} (300) ; Zn^{2+} (100) ; Cd^{2+} or Hg^{2+} (50) ; Al^{3+} (15) ; Sn^{2+} (5) ; Pb^{2+} (10) ; V^{4+} or V^{5+} (20) ; UO_2^{2+} (2) ; Mo^{6+} (10) ; Mn^{2+} (10) ; Fe^{3+} (20) ; Co^{2+} or Ni^{2+} (50) ; Rh^{3+} (15) ; Pd^{2+} (5) ; Ir^{3+} (10) and Pt^{4+} (15). NO_2^- , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6^{2-}$, phthalate, BO_3^{3-} , citrate, Cu^{2+} and Os^{8+} interfered.

In determination of 3.3 ppm of Ru(III) using its violet complex with the diol, the following ions were tolerated : F^- (250) ; Cl^- (5000) ; Br^- (3000) ; I^- (300) ; NO_3^- (1000) ; SCN^- (50) ; SO_4^{2-} (1000) ; Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} or Ba^{2+} (300) ; Zn^{2+} (100) ; Cd^{2+} (20) ; Sn^{2+} (5) ; Pb^{2+} (10) ; Rh^{3+} (15) ; Pd^{2+} (5) ; Ir^{3+} (10) and Pt^{4+}

(15). Cu^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} , V^{4+} , Mn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} get precipitated and interfered. NO_2^- , CH_3COO^- , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_8^{2-}$, phthalate, BO_3^{3-} , citrate and Os^{8+} also interfered.

Detection of Os(VIII): The diol forms a red complex with Os(VIII) in alkaline medium without heating. The method is applied to detect the metal in presence of many diverse ions including those from platinum group metals and in synthetic mixtures of osmium-iridium alloys.

Place a drop of the test solution on a spot plate, add 1-2 drops of the diol (0.02 M) followed by 1-2 drops of NaOH solution (0%). Red colour produced within 1 min. shows the presence of Os(VIII).

Limit of identification : 1.89 μg .

Limit of dilution : 1: 27250

Diverse ions : At least 800 times excess of Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , SCN^- , CH_3COO^- , SO_4^{2-} , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_8^{2-}$, BO_3^{3-} , PO_4^{3-} and citrate does not interfere in detection of Os. The extents to which other ions (concentration excess over Os) tolerated are: F^- (20), alkaline earth metals or Zn^{2+} (50), Cd^{2+} (30), Hg^{2+} (15), Cu^{2+} (10), Al^{3+} (25), Sn^{2+} (10), Pb^{2+} (6), V^{4+} or V^{5+} (20), Mo^{6+} (15), Mn^{2+} (2), Fe^{2+} (15), Co^{2+} (20), Ni^{2+} (15), Ru^{3+} (4), Rh^{3+} (10), Pd^{2+} (20), Ir^{3+} (10), Pt^{4+} (12) and (10). However, the presence of Fe^{2+} interferes.

Chelatometric titrations : A large number of azo-dyes have been reported as indicators in complexometric titrations of Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Hg^{2+} . The diazotised sulphanilic acid coupled with the pyrimidinediol produces a red dye (II). The dye-solution is used as an indicator in the titration of these metals against EDTA.

Indicator solution : Add 1 ml of 1% NaNO_2 solution to 6 ml of 1% sulphanilic acid, followed by 9 ml of 0.5% of the diol. Adjust pH to 7 with ammonia solution and make up the volume to 50 ml.

Standard solutions : Weighed amount of the metal (Zn, Cd or Hg) was dissolved in HClO_4 solution evaporated to dryness, the residue dissolved in the acid of known strength and made up to the volume. The 0.10 M titrant was prepared from analytical grade EDTA (disodium salt).

Procedure : To a suitable aliquot of metal solution, add 5-10 drops of the indicator followed by dropwise addition of $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl-NH}_4\text{OH}$ buffer (pH 10.0) till a blue precipitate or colour appears. Add 2 more drops of the buffer. Titrate slowly, while shaking, against EDTA until the blue colour disappears. The end-point is colourless or light red if excess indicator is used. Check the end-point by addition of 2 drops of buffer. If the blue colour appears, continue titration till it is colourless. The titration can be performed at pH 9.5-10.0 and at temperature between 10 and 60°C. Minimum titrable amounts (in mg/20 ml) for Zn, Cd and Hg are 20, 10 and 25 respectively.

Diverse ions : In titration of 30 mg of Zn, 2000 mg of Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , phthalate, BO_3^{3-} or PO_4^{3-} ; 200 of F^- , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ or $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_8^{2-}$; 150 of thiourea and 50 of citrate do not interfere. In Cd titration (25 mg), 1000 mg of I^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} or phthalate; 500 of Br^- , $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_8^{2-}$, BO_3^{3-} or citrate; 100 of F^- , Cl^- , thiourea or phosphate; and in Hg titration (30 mg), 2500 mg of F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , CNS^- , SO_4^{2-} or phthalate; 500 of BO_3^{3-} and 250 of $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_8^{2-}$ or citrate do not interfere. SO_3^{2-} and cations interfere in all titrations.

Synthesis of ammonium salt of (III) and its use : The azo-dye is synthesised as its salt (IV) and used in the volumetric titrations of MoO_4^{2-} , WO_4^{2-} and PO_4^{3-} with lead nitrate solution.

To 12.7 g of the diol solution in 1 N HCl at 0° add cold NaNO_2 solution (10%) dropwise. Test for complete diazotisation by starch-KI paper. Keep temperature below 5° and avoid excess of HNO_2 .

(IV)

Dissolve 14.5 g of β -naphthol in minimum alcohol and add to it excess of concentrated NH_4OH solution (5%). Mix the diazotised solution with β -naphthol solution when the red crystals of the dye-salt appear almost immediately. Wash first with water and then with a little alcohol. Recrystallise from alcohol-water mixture. Elemental analysis corresponds with the proposed structure (IV). (Found : C, 51.52%; H, 4.12%; N, 20.46%. Calc. : C, 50.23%; H, 3.89%; N, 20.93%.)

Standard solutions : 0.01% Dye solution in ethanol was used as indicator. The other solutions (0.01-0.10 M) were prepared from analytical grade sodium molybdate, sodium tungstate, potassium dihydrogen phosphate and lead nitrate and standardised. Hexamethylene tetraamine and pyridine buffers were used after adjusting their pH between 6.0 and 7.0 with dilute HNO_3 .

Procedure : Adjust pH of the solution containing requisite amount of the anion with 0.5-1.0 ml buffer. Add 0.5-1.0 ml indicator solution and dilute to 10 ml. Titrate slowly, with shaking, against lead nitrate solution till the colour changes from orange to mauve precipitate.

The titration can be carried out at 10°-80°. Titrable amounts (in mg/10 ml) for MoO_4^{2-} (at pH 5.5-7.0), WO_4^{2-} (at pH 6.0-7.0) and PO_4^{3-} (at pH 6.2-7.0) are 0.7-4.5, 5.0-10.0 and 2.8-5.2, respectively.

Diverse ions: The tolerance limits of various ions in determination of 1.5 mg MoO_4^{2-} 5.0 mg WO_4^{2-} and 2.8 mg PO_4^{3-} , are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS

Diverse ion	Tolerance limits (in mg) in determination of		
	Molybdate	Tungstate	Phosphate
Fluoride	5	5	10
Chloride	40	3	10
Bromide	40	2	8
Iodide	40	1	10
Nitrite	5	1	5
Nitrate	40	40	40
Thiocyanate	40	8	10
Acetate	40	8	10
Sulphate	5	5	5
Thiosulphate	5	1	10
Oxalate	1	0.1	0.5
Thiourea	40	10	10
Borate	40	5	10
Citrate	0.5	0.5	0.5
Ca (II) or Sr (II)	1.5	1.5	1.5
Ba (II)	1.0	0.6	0.3
Zn (II)	1.3	Interferes	0.1
Cd (II)	1.5	10	0.1
Hg (II)	4	Interferes	4
Tl (I)	2	2	2
Co (II)	0.3	Interferes	0.7

Fe (II) and Ni (II) interfere seriously in each case.

Discussion

In titrations involving MoO_4^{2-} and PO_4^{3-} , the end-point corresponds to the formation of PbMoO_4 and PbWO_4 in accordance with :

In PO_4^{3-} titration, the ratio of Pb to PO_4^{3-} is 5:3 at the equivalence point corresponding to the formation of apatite-type phosphate, $^{7-10} \text{Pb}_5(\text{PO}_4)_3\text{OH}$.

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